

1 **Components of the mitochondria are transcriptionally modulated by muramyl dipeptide in**
2 **monocytes and macrophages.**

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7 A central tenet of the systems biologic study of immunology and self non-self discrimination conducted by
8 our laboratory is that a complete understanding of the cellular and transcriptional processes regulated and
9 affected by pattern recognition of bacteria through sensing of muramyl dipeptide (MDP) is required for
10 control of diseases involving perturbed innate immune function. We describe here transcriptional
11 modulation of components of the mitochondria by MDP in primary monocytes and macrophages from
12 humans. In the monocyte, MDP exposure resulted in activation of a mitochondrial ribosomal protein switch
13 involving Mrpl14 induction together with Mrpl34 silencing. We observed Timm17a induction along with
14 Induction j of the Tomm40 translocase of outer mitochondrial membrane. The mitochondrial DNA helicase
15 TWNK was a target of MDP sensing, as was the mitochondrial G-elongation factor GFM1. Defined
16 understanding and description of cellular processes affected by immune and sterile stimuli is required for
17 control of cellular homeostasis and normal biologic function.
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